

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Annotation

The reforms being carried out in our country today change the intellectual potential of our people in all areas with a new outlook and demand the development of active communicative qualities. In this process, the spiritual memory of our people is being restored, it is being manifested in various aspects of spiritual life.

Keywords: Linguistics, competence, competent-active, social, professional, competence, sociology, social psychology, education, professional education.

Head of state Shavkat Mirziyoyev has paid great attention to the education of young people and their socialization process in our country and said that "a very important issue that never falls off the agenda for us is related to the education of our young generation, our children. We should never forget one fact: a child who is left out of the attention of parents and society brings only worry instead of joy and benefit to the family. "That is why child education and working with young people must remain the most important and urgent task for us", it can be understood that youth policy is one of the most important tasks. In such conditions, it will be possible to develop communication skills in young people, and through this, they will be able to develop communication skills, the ability to establish tolerant relations, and feelings of tolerance.

The reforms being carried out in our country today change the intellectual potential of our people in all areas with a new outlook and demand the development of active communicative qualities. In this process, the spiritual memory of our people is being restored, it is being manifested in various aspects of spiritual life. The head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoev expressed his confidence in our youth and said, "Only you, our dear youth, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, think independently, and always live with a sense of courage for the fate of the country, will boldly go out into the field today and "You are capable of solving the tasks that life itself puts before us every day," he says. In such conditions, it is very important to support the initiative and enthusiasm, patience and perseverance, courage and creativity aimed at developing active communication skills in students. A number of decisions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev were of great importance in the development of youth policy in our country.

In our country, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 14, 2016 "On State Policy Regarding Youth", March 14, 2017 "On Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Secondary Special Vocational Education Institutions" ", dated July 18, 2017 "On comprehensive measures to improve the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan", dated July 28, 2017 "Increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and taking the development of the field to a new level on development" of September 13, 2017 "On comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book

products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture" and On July 5, 2017 "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan", on January 25, 2018 "On general secondary, secondary special and vocational training" Decrees of June 27, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the education system", "Youth are our future" State Program, Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 23, 2018 "Youth in the military The adoption of the decisions on approving the concept of educating in the spirit of patriotism served to turn our youth into a socially active layer. After all, "we will not only continue the work started in order to realize the dreams, progressive ideas and initiatives of young people, but we will raise them to a new, higher level". Organizational and methodical tasks aimed at developing students and their communication skills are shown. At the same time, the issue of youth is put on the agenda in the "Strategy of Actions". The experience of social life proves that this conceptual strategy of the head of state is correct and has great theoretical and methodological significance. That is why it is becoming a priority to improve communication culture and skills of young people on the basis of high human feelings. That is why the development of the society and the improvement of the skills of the young generation to engage in social relations, saving the worldview, spirituality, and moral thinking from the influence of destructive ideas were put on the agenda as an important social task. The Strategy of Actions for the Renewal and Development of Uzbekistan is not only the socio-historical experience of the nation and the country, but also the methodological foundations shown by Sh.M. Mirziyoev in the practice of social policy aimed at young people, became an example of a new and original concept. In this regard, the concept aimed at increasing the communicative competence of young people became very important in revealing the nature of social relations. This concept opened wide opportunities for young people to take a place as an active communication layer and become the owner of the profession they want. After all, "the strategy of the new Uzbekistan is to expand the participation of citizens in the social and political life of the country, to realize their dreams and aspirations, to realize their progressive initiatives, to solve their life problems, to raise their standard of living, to independently achieve their material well-being. it means creating sufficient and necessary conditions for its increase".

This paragraph analyzes the social necessity and pedagogical importance of developing communicative competence of teenage students. Also, it is aimed to highlight the current state of the pedagogical processes and the aspects that need to be reformed, related to the preparation of teenagers for communication culture and increasing their accessibility to social relations. For this, it is appropriate to consider the content, psychological classification of the concept of young people and the problematic aspects of their education.

In the literature, it is noted that the age of a teenager corresponds to the 5th-8th grades. "Adolescence ranges from approximately 11-12 to 14-15 years of age, but the transition to adolescence may not coincide with the transition to 5th grade and may occur a year earlier or later. . The special situation of adolescence is expressed in its names: "transition", "sharply changing", "difficult", "critical". They note the complexity and importance of the developmental processes that occur at this age. It is related to the transition from one period of life to another. In all areas of human development (physical, mental, spiritual, moral, social) great qualitative and quantitative changes are taking place." During this period, psychological changes and social relations also expand. At the same time, mental potential and personal

positions in moral relations are formed in adolescents. In the process of mental and physical changes of adolescents during this period, it is effective to prepare and influence communication skills. They develop activeness in social relations, openness to communication, and a culture of tolerant and tolerant communication.

At the same time, the correct orientation of the process of self-realization in adolescents, the high quality of education aimed at realizing their "I" creates an opportunity to distinguish individual feelings and qualities. "An important factor in the development of a teenager's personality is his personal activity - the process of identity, self-recognition and identification is active - but this process is not uniform. On the one hand, "adulthood" begins to appear in teenagers, and on the other hand, "childhood" remains. Adolescent development can have different general directions, and each direction can have many options. This issue is of great pedagogical importance." This makes them want to act like adults, stay away from the younger ones, communicate with adults, listen to them and be around them. At the same time, their personality and sexual changes also affect their behavior and communication skills. During this period, it is necessary not to disturb the mental stability and balance of children. "Important changes occur during adolescence, which are related to the physical growth and biological maturation of the organism. Jumps in the growth of the body, changes in the endocrine system, activity in the pituitary gland, puberty, strengthening of the heart, muscles, and the whole body lead to important changes in the psychic, mental and spiritual growth of a person. Nevertheless, the development of theoretical ideas in the explanation of "stress" in adolescence creates such a generalization that according to it, the manifestation and passage of adolescence are influenced by social conditions in life, the development of a teenager, his adult life. depends on the position in the world". So, the conditions during the adolescent's development, the social environment, and the factors influencing it affect it.

In pedagogic textbooks and manuals, education is interpreted as a means of mutual cooperation between teachers and students and a means of mutual positive influence on each other. However, the socio-psychological system of this activity is not always taken into account. Here too, a number of problems arise that can negatively affect the content and methodical aspects of education and training. Mutual cooperation envisages social and psychological unity of teachers and students. In many cases, it is not paid attention to in the course of the lesson.

In the system of pedagogical communication of teachers of general education schools, the perception and thinking of one or another student is often formed in one mold, in the eyes of the teacher, they become objects of stable psychological communication. Therefore, if the student becomes "bad-behaved" in the eyes of the teacher, it affects the teacher's communication practice towards him.

In order for a teenager to have a healthy mindset, the content of individual characteristics in his way of thinking is of great importance. "The main reasons for the need to increase attention to the problem of adolescents:

- the influence of culture, art and literature, changing socio-economic conditions as a result of the development of science and technology;
- due to the expansion of mass media, the level of awareness of teenagers has increased;
- accelerated physical and mental development of adolescents;

- the necessity of a special approach to ideological-political, patriotic and international education when working with teenagers;
- the problems of transparency, social justice, and democracy are deeply penetrating the social life;
- a wide opportunity is created for students to learn independently, think creatively, self-manage, understand, evaluate and control. Therefore, the development of students' scientific outlook and thinking leads to the development of communication culture and the formation of the skills of engaging in active relationships.

An important condition for modeling the future communication with students is the mutual emotional unity of the teacher and students, which gives the teacher the opportunity to foresee the following possible atmosphere of the lesson:

- to be able to anticipate various situations that may occur with a group of students in the upcoming lesson;
- organization of various levels of democratic and free interaction with students, setting prospects for its development;
- to create students' interest in learning and creative mood in the lesson.

The development of communicative competence of teenage students can be considered as one of the methods of development and self-expression of the participants of the educational process. Thus, communicative competence becomes one of the main parts of personal success, competitiveness and personal satisfaction, as well as high professional level, which depends on the quality of education. Active and effective listening and being tolerant is one of the main conditions of constructive communication.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2017. - B. 135.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Roof 1. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - B.537.
3. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. From Mirziyoyev's speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2017. - USA, 2017. -B. 387
4. Mirziyoev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. -Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2021. -B. 84
4. <http://elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/item/12519-2021-06-02-11-23-40> (Psychological characteristics of teenagers)
- 5.<http://elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/item/12519-2021-06-02-11-23-40> (Psychological characteristics of teenagers)
6. <http://elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/item/12519-2021-06-02-11-23-40> (Psychological characteristics of teenagers)
- 7.Ананьев Б.Г. Человек как предмет познания. – Л.: ЛГУ. 1968.
- 8.Фозиев Э. Психология. (Ёш даврлари психологияси). Тошкент.: «Ўқитувчи», 1994. – Б.134.
- 9.Evatov, S. S. (2020). MODERN SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL MEASURES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE AMONG STUDENTS. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(7), 484-489.

10. Evatov, S. S. (2021). FORMATION OF STUDENTS COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS, 2(05), 13-19.
11. Sobirovich, E. S. (2021). Developing Communicative Competence of Students: Historical and Pedagogical Experience. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 2(5), 108-111.
12. Sobirovich, E. S. (2021). INNOVATION EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(05), 483-487.
13. Sobirovich, E. S. (2022). CONTENT AND SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE CONCEPT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE Teacher at Fergana State University. World Bulletin of Social Sciences, 9, 176-180.
14. Sobirovich, E. S. (2022). On The Basis of Family and School Cooperation Theoretical and Methodological Fundamentals of Developing Communicative Competence of Adolescent Students. Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication, 2(4), 73-77.
15. Абдулазизова, Н., & Эватов, С. (2014). КАСБ-ЎНАР КОЛЛЕЖИ ЎЎУВЧИЛАРИДА ЗАРАРЛИ ОДАТЛАРНИ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ. ВЕСТНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА, 25(4), 38-41.
16. Эватов, С. С. (2016). THE ROLE OF FAMILY IN SOCIETY AND CHILD'S EDUCATION IN FAMILY. Учёный XXI века, (5-1 (18)), 46-49.
17. Эватов, С. С. (2022). ОИЛА ВА МАКТАБ ҲАМКОРЛИГИ АСОСИДА ЎСМИР ЁШИДАГИ ЎЎУВЧИЛАРНИНГ КОММУНИКАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ШАРТ-ШАРОИТЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1(В3), 182-190.
18. Эватов, С. С., & Ибрагимова, С. И. (2022). ЎСМИР ЁШИДАГИ ЎЎУВЧИЛАРНИНГ КОММУНИКАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК МАЗМУНИ. ТА'ЛИМ ВА INNOVATION TADQIQOTLAR, 8-9.
19. Эватов, С. С., & Набиева, А. (2022). ЎЎУВЧИ ЁШЛАРНИ КРЕАТИВЛИГИ ВА КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯВИЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШДАГИ ИСЛОХАТЛАРИ. ТА'ЛИМ ВА INNOVATION TADQIQOTLAR, 10-11.

